

Synthesis of new hydroxyacetophenones by using iodine and iodic acid

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Iodine and iodic acid mixture has been used as a reagent for iodination of hydroxyacetophenones, and some new hydroxy-iodoacetophenones are prepared.

Iodoacetophenones can be prepared by Fries rearrangement¹ of iodophenylacetates but the yields are poor. They can also be prepared by iodination of hydroxyacetophenones. Iodine monochloride² is good iodinating agent but it is hazardous. Iodine and ammonia³ can also be used but most of the times hydroxy aromatics form solid ammonium salt and iodination halts. Recently, pyridine-iodine monochloride complex³ has been utilised as an iodinating agent but the isolation of iodoproduct is difficult. Iodination of resorcinol derivatives and some hydroxychromones has been reported. Iodination has also been carried out by using iodine and NaOH⁴, and iodine, potassium iodide and potassium iodate⁵ in acetic acid.

Treatment of hydroxyacetophenones (**1a-h**) and iodine with iodic acid gave the corresponding iodoacetophenones (**2a-h**) (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

All the hydroxyiodoacetophenones gave satisfactory elemental analyses. The iodination of hydroxyiodoacetophenone by iodine and iodic acid is significant for the following reasons: (i) the procedure is simple, (ii) isolation of the product is easy and (iii) the method is superior to other reported methods.

Experimental

M.p.s. are uncorrected. IR spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and ¹H NMR spectra on a Hitachi NMR-1200 spectrometer (90 MHz) using TMS as an internal standard.

General procedure for the iodination of hydroxyacetophenone by iodine and iodic acid: To a mixture of 2'-hydroxyacetophenone (0.001 mol) and iodine (0.001 or 0.002 mol) dissolved in ethanol (30 ml) was added to iodic acid (0.001 or 0.002 mol) dissolved in water (1 ml) and stirred for 0.5 h at 35–40°. It was further stirred for 1 h and diluted with cold water. The resulting solid products (yields 75–85%) were washed successively with saturated sodium bisulfite solution and cold water and crystallised from ethanol: **2a**, m.p 105°, $\nu_{\max}$ 1635 (C=O), 1580 (C=C), 1300 cm⁻¹ (phenyl CO), δ 2.70 (3H, s, COCH₃), 7.85 (1H, d, 4ArH), 8.20 (1H, d, 6ArH), 12.85 (1H, s, OH); **b**, 89°; **c**, 80°, δ 2.25 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 2.75 (3H, s, ArCOCH₃), 7.45 (1H, d, 4ArH), 7.75 (2H, s, 6H), 12.85 (1H, s, OH); **d**, 112°; **e**, 76°; **f**, 149°, δ 2.35 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 2.75 (3H, s, COCH₃), 7.40 (1H, d, 2ArH), 7.70 (1H, d, 6ArH), 12.85 (1H, s, OH); **g**, 128° (lit. 127°); **h**, 162° (lit. 164°).

References

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